

A STUDY OF THE ATTITUDE OF MIDDLE CLASS STUDENTS OF
YAMUNANAGAR DISTRICT OF HARYANA TOWARDS
ENGLISH AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

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Abstract

Human are social beings and have the power to think. As a result of the thinking process they produce some ideas and everyone wants to express one's ideas to others. But for the expression of his ideas or knowledge or emotions, one needs some medium and language presents itself as a powerful medium of expression. Thus one can rightly say that language is one of the unique possessions of man. What distinguishes a man from others animals is language? Everyone makes use of it, be it a beggar or a king. It makes possible the keeping of records and the creation of a store of knowledge. It is the basis of all creative thoughts without language there would be no progress, no civilization, no culture. The cultural heritage of man resides in language only. Language plays a vital role in our society. Without language personality cannot be developed and society cannot be enriched in human personality has much to do with effective use of language.

Key words: -Attitude, Class, Students, School, Language, Education.

Introduction

A language is the standing record as well as contemporary expression of the culture and experience of the particular group speaking, cultural patterns are woven. Language has been recognized as an important social phenomenon. Long before the advent of scientific discipline of linguistic as an academic subject in language could be planned and its direction changed according to the changing social situation of a given time and space. Fundamentally, language is a man's unique accomplishment more than anything else. It sets man apart from the animal world. It is the vehicle of communication and speech. Language is essential for us to express our thoughts and feelings clearly, precisely, beautifully and effectively. Language is a tool of scientific behaviour. It is a check on thoughts unless ideas have clarity. Their

proper expression is not possible. It is through language that the culture and civilization of the people can be prescribed, enriched and propagated. Mr. Mario said, “The story of language is the story of civilization.” Language is an important element that without it all cultural activities would remain dormant and all human experience would be rendered insignificant. Language is also necessary for securing national integrity and solidarity.

A great controversy is raised regarding which language should be kept as a medium of instruction. For this number of conferences, seminar is also being held. The present venture is an exercise in this direction so as to know the attitude of students towards English as a medium of instruction.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

India is a multi-lingual country. So a great controversy is raised these days in India as to which language should be the medium of communication in the different walks of life, which language should be the medium of official work and which language should be the medium of instruction at higher level. For solving this problem several conferences are being held. Different political leaders, educationists and literary men are giving their views. Till now no definite decision has been taken and still it decision has been taken and still it is a big question yet to be answered. In order to find out the above raised queries, there is a need of conduction research in this area. The present investigation is an attempt in this direction only. The aim of the present study is to find out the attitude of middle class students of Yamunanagar district of Haryana towards English as a medium of instruction.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are as follows:-

1. To find out the attitudinal differences of middle class boys and girls students towards English as a medium of instruction.
2. To find out the attitudinal difference of students studying in CBSE schools and Haryana Board schools towards English as a medium of instruction.
3. To find out the attitudinal difference of middle class rural and urban students towards English as a medium of instruction.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant difference between the middle class boys and girls students towards English as a medium of instruction.
2. There is no significant difference between middle class students studying in CBSE and Haryana board schools towards English as a medium of instruction.
3. There is no significant difference between middle class rural and urban students towards English as a medium of instruction.

PLAN AND PROCEDURE

In the present study, the normative survey method was employed to collect the data. The sample of present study constituted of 200 boys and girls of middle class from two schools of Yamunanagar district of Haryana. As far as population for this work was concerned two schools of Yamunanagar district were taken up. Out of these schools, a sample of 200 boys and girls was picked up on random basis from two schools of Yamunanagar district.

TOOLS USED

In order to assess the attitudes of the students, the attitude scale was developed by the investigator. The procedure of development and standardization of scale followed usual steps: Preparation of the first draft: - The scale was prepared after passing through following three stages i.e. item formulation, item selection (60 items) and item analysis. Validity: The face validity method was employed to validate the attitude scale.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Analysis of data for the present study was made on conformity with the objectives as laid down earlier. After collection of data, the same was put into the tabular form to make the process of analysis easier and accurate. Keeping in view the nature of data, the following statistical techniques were used: -

- (i) The measure of central tendency-Arithmetic mean.
- (ii) The measure of Dispersion-Standard Deviation.

(iii) t-ratio.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data for the present study was analyzed as per the objectives of the study as under: -

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE ATTITUDE OF MIDDLE CLASS GIRLS AND BOYS STUDENTS.

The significance of difference in the mean attitude score of girls and boys student has been presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1
MEAN SCORES AND t-RATIO OF MIDDLE CLASS GIRLS AND BOYS STUDENT

Scores	Frequencies of girl students	Frequencies of Boys students
25-29	1	4
30-34	9	8
35-39	26	23
40-44	44	46
45-49	14	13
50-54	6	4
55-59	0	2

Mean of girls = 40.95 Mean of boys = 40.8

S.D. of girls = 5.113 S.D. of boys = 5.749

S.E. (σ_0) = 0.769

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{N_2}}$$

Here,

$\sigma_1 =$ S.D. of girls

$\sigma_2 = \frac{3}{4}$ S.D. of boys

$N_1 =$ Number of girls

$N_2 =$ Number of boys

$$t = \frac{|M_1 - M_2|}{\sigma_0}$$

Here,

$M_1 =$ Mean of girls

$M_2 =$ Mean of boys

$\sigma_0 =$ Standard Error

$t = 1.13$

Calculated value < Critical value

TABLE 1

Students	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Significance at 0.01 level	Significance at 0.05 level
Girls	40.95	5.113	0.827	Not Significant	
Boys	40.8	5.749			

It is observed from the Table 1 that the mean of the attitude of girls and boys student towards English as a medium of instruction is found to be 40.95 and 40.8 respectively. The S.D. of girls and boys student comes out to be 5.113 and 5.749 respectively. The standard error is calculated 0.769. The t-ratio comes out to be 1.13. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

It indicated that girls and boys student of middle class had positive attitude towards English as a medium of instruction. Therefore, Hypothesis no.1 that there is no significant different between the attitude of girls and boys student towards English as a medium of instruction is accepted.

RESULT: Hypothesis No.1 is accepted.

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE ATTITUDE OF MIDDLE CLASS STUDENTS STUDYING IN CBSE AND HBSE SCHOOLS.

The significance of difference between the mean scores of students studying in CBSE and HBSE schools has been presented in the Table 2. It follows as under:-

MEAN SCORES AND t-RATIO OF STUDENTS STUDYING IN CBSE AND HBSE SCHOOLS

Scores	Frequencies of girl students	Frequencies of Boys students
25-29	3	2
30-34	8	9
35-39	24	25
40-44	42	48
45-49	17	10
50-54	5	5
55-59	1	1

Mean of students of CBSE schools = 4.15

S.D. = 5.598

Mean of students of HBSE schools = 40.7

S.D. = 5.274

S.E. = $\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{N_2}}$ = 0.7691

Here,

$\sigma_1 =$ S.D. of students of CBSE schools

$\sigma_2 = \frac{3}{4}$ S.D. of students of HBSE schools

$N_1 =$ Number of students of CBSE schools

$N_2 =$ Number of students of HBSE schools

$$t = \frac{|M_1 - M_2|}{\sigma_0} = 0.421$$

Here,

$M_1 =$ Mean of students of CBSE schools

$M_2 =$ Mean of students of HBSE schools

$\sigma_0 =$ Standard Error

Calculated value < Critical Value

TABLE 2

Students	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Significance at 0.01 level	Significance at 0.05 level
CBSE	41.5	5.598	0.421	Not Significant	Not Significant
HBSE	40.7	5.274			

It is observed from the Table 2 that the mean of attitude of students studying in CBSE and HBSE schools comes out to be 41.5 and 40.7 respectively. The standard deviation is 5.598 and 5.274 respectively. The standard error is calculated 0.7691. The t-ratio is 0.421. The calculated value is less than the critical value. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

It indicated that the middle class students studying in CBSE and HBSE schools had equal attitude towards English as a medium of instruction. Therefore, hypothesis No.2 that there is no significant difference between the attitude of students studying in CBSE and HBSE schools towards English as a medium of instruction is accepted.

RESULT: Null Hypothesis is accepted.

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE ATTITUDE OF MIDDLE CLASS RURAL AND URBAN STUDENTS.

Table 3 shows the significance of difference between in the mean attitude score of middle class rural and urban students.

MEAN SCORES AND t-RATIO OF MIDDLE CLASS RURAL AND URBAN STUDENTS

Scores	Frequencies of rural students	Frequencies of urban students
25-29	3	2
30-34	11	6
35-39	23	26
40-44	44	46
45-49	12	15
50-54	5	5
55-59	2	0

Mean of rural students = 40.7

S.D. = 5.857

Mean of urban students = 41.05

S.D. = 4.985

S.E. $\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{N_2}}$ = 0.7691

Here,

σ_1 = S.D. of rural students

σ_2 $\frac{3}{4}$ S.D. of urban students

N_1 = Number of rural students

N_2 = Number of urban students

$$t = \frac{|M_1 - M_2|}{\sigma_0} = 1.13$$

Here,

M_1 = Mean of rural students

M_2 = Mean of urban students

σ_0 = Standard Error

Calculated value < Critical Value

TABLE 3

Students	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Significance at 0.01 level	Significance at 0.05 level
Rural	40.7	5.857	1.13	Not Significant	Not Significant
Urban	41.05	4.985			

It is observed from the Table 3 that the mean of attitude of middle class rural and urban students towards English as a medium of instruction is found 40.7 and 41.05 respectively. The S.D. of rural and urban students comes out to be 5.857 and 4.985 respectively. The standard error is calculated 0.769. The t-ratio is 1.13. The calculated value was less than critical value. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted.

It indicated that the middle class rural and urban students had equal attitude towards English as a medium of instruction. Therefore, Hypothesis No.3 that there is no significant difference between the attitude of middle-class rural and urban students towards English as a medium of instruction is accepted.

RESULT: Null hypothesis is accepted.

MAIN FINDINGS

The results of the study indicate that there existed a positive attitude of middle class students towards English as a medium of instruction.

(i) The result of study shows that girls students have the mean score 40.95 and S.D. 5.113, while the boys students have the mean score 40.8 and S.D. 5.749. This shows that there is no significant difference between the attitude of middle class girls and boys students towards English as a medium of instruction.

(ii) The result of the study indicates that the students studying in CBSE schools have the mean score 41.5 and S.D. 5.598. While the mean score of students studying in Haryana Board schools is 40.7 and S.D. 5.274. This shows that there is no significant difference between the attitude of students studying in CBSE schools and HBSE schools towards English as a medium of instruction.

(iii) The result of the study shows that the mean score of middle class rural students comes out to be 40.7 and S.D. is 5.857. While the mean score of middle class urban students is 41.05 and S.D, is 4.985. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the attitude of middle class rural and urban students towards English as a medium of instruction.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

A great controversy is going on as to which language should be made the medium of instruction at higher level. In order to solve this problem several meetings, conferences, seminars are being held and a number of scholars are express their views. On the basis of the discussions and the findings of the present investigation, there are three possible alternative for the medium of school education. These are English, Hindi and regional language. There is no denying in fact that English language has been one of the important factors in the development of unity of our country. In fact the concept of nationality and the sentiments of nationality and the sentiments of nationalism are largely the gift of English language and literature in India. English has supplied us with the key to the fundamental ideas of modern civilization, to modern science and philosophy. Therefore, the medium of instruction should be English at school level.

The present study has its implication for educational planners, curriculum makers and educational officers. While framing policies this think should be kept in mind that most of

the courses at school level must use identical Medias of instructions. For this purpose we can take English as a medium of instruction because it is the only link language and the language which is understood by a large number of people in South. Maximum material and modern knowledge is available in this language.

No doubt this language has not yet been so equipped as to become a suitable vehicle for the purpose. There is an important way of equipping the language. Just as a child cannot learn to swim unless he plunges into the water, an un-developed language cannot develop unless put to use.

At last we can say that English can replace Hindi as a medium of instruction at middle level. But undue haste should not be made. It will take a long time to make English suitable for teaching in all faculties. We should not at once banish Hindi otherwise it will result in a negative way of intellectual development. Our scientific and technological development will suffer and the country will not progress.

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